

Impact of Non-CO₂ Pricing on Routing and Ticket Fares in Aviation: Strategies to Address Uncertainties in Climate Policies

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Keywords

Transport Policy, Aviation Emissions, Non-CO₂ Mitigation, Carbon Pricing, EU ETS, Ticket Fares

Abstract

Historically, CO₂ accounts for only one-third of the climate impact of air traffic, with the majority stemming from non-CO₂ effects such as contrail-induced cloudiness, nitrogen oxides, water vapor, and particulates. In response, the EU revised its Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), requiring Member States to ensure that aircraft operators monitor and report CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) emissions per flight, starting January 1, 2025. By December 2027, the EU might propose a second legislative extension of the EU ETS, introducing non-CO₂ pricing based on CO₂e to incentivize mitigation actions. Following the 'Polluter-Pays Principle', the CO₂e pricing will affect aircraft operators (AOs), influencing ticket prices and encouraging climate-optimized flight routings. This paper examines the impact of non-CO₂ pricing on flight routing, climate impact, and ticket prices across various weather conditions, CO₂e accounting options, climate metrics, and carbon prices. Operational mitigation potentials are primarily driven by weather conditions, while ticket price increases are influenced by the accounted share of CO₂e and carbon price. Gradual implementation could help moderate passenger costs at first. Resulting ticket price increases vary between 1.0% and 4.8%. CO₂e abatement costs range from 3 to 74 € per tonne CO₂e, with a median of 14€ and lower costs on days with effective contrail avoidance. These cost estimates are below expected abatement cost in other sectors such as wind or solar energy and direct air capture. Incorporating cooling contrails into pricing could neutralize or reduce costs through compensation but is controversially discussed due to higher risks. Given large uncertainties in non-CO₂ modeling, which affect data accuracy in an monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) framework but could incentivize harmful re-routing under CO₂e pricing, strategies to mitigate risks in climate policies are proposed. These include using ensemble weather forecasts to reduce formation risks or risks of unnecessary detours, and implementing uncertainty-based CO₂e accounting, which relies on confidence levels in climate-impact modeling. Ongoing research and adaptable policies are crucial to incorporate the latest scientific understanding and drive meaningful climate action in aviation.

1 Introduction

Non-CO₂ effects from contrail-induced cirrus cloudiness (CIC), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), water vapor (H₂O), and particulates account for two-thirds of aviation’s effective radiative forcing (ERF) from 1940 to 2018 (Lee et al., 2021). Mitigating non-CO₂ effects through operational measures is promising but poses economic challenges caused by higher fuel consumption and longer flight times. Due to saturation effects, the first persistent contrails contribute to warming the most, while the climate impact diminishes with each additional flight through the same region. As a result, individual avoidance efforts by a single operator—though valuable for pioneering contrail avoidance practices and gaining operational experience—often fail to reduce the bulk of the overall climate impact if other flights continue to form persistent contrails in the same region. Without regulatory support or financial incentives, operational mitigation may put operators at a competitive disadvantage. Hence, effective contrail mitigation requires coordinated action across multiple operative institutions to collectively avoid persistent contrail formation areas (PCFAs), underscoring the need for climate policy.

In December 2022, the EU revised its CO₂ emissions trading system (EU ETS) to align with its climate target of a 55% emission reduction by 2030 compared to 1990 (European Union, 2023). On the one hand, this will be achieved by significantly reducing the cap of annual emissions allowances for aviation by increasing the rate of the linear reduction factor (LRF) from 2.2% to 4.3% between 2024 and 2027, as well as by rapidly phasing out free allocation of aviation allowances (EUAA) by the end of 2026. On the other hand, also non-CO₂ aviation climate effects shall be covered by a monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) framework as a first step towards full integration into the EU ETS. From January 1, 2025, Member States must ensure that aircraft operators (AOs) monitor and report CO₂ equivalent emissions (CO₂e) per flight considering both CO₂ and non-CO₂ effects. As the current EU ETS focuses on CO₂ emissions only, the majority of the climate impact of aviation is currently not considered, which is intended to change through the mentioned EU decision. Implementing an effective non-CO₂ MRV system is an essential first step for tracking progress towards climate-neutral aviation, thus establishing mitigation incentives and demonstrating compliance with international agreements such as the Paris Agreement. By December 31, 2027, the Commission shall therefore submit an assessment report on the application of the MRV framework and, if appropriate, a legislative proposal to mitigate non-CO₂ effects of aviation by extending the scope of the EU ETS to non-CO₂ impacts of aviation. This decision is discussed controversially for the following reasons:

1. Unlike the effect of CO₂, non-CO₂ climate effects are still subject to large uncertainties, which are about 8 times higher than for CO₂ (Lee et al., 2021). According to the decision of the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), however, a lack of full scientific certainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation (United Nations, 1992, Annex 1, Principle 15). This raises the question if the scientific understanding is adequate for integrating non-CO₂ effects into policy frameworks.
2. Non-CO₂ effects have much shorter atmospheric lifetimes than CO₂ (e.g., hours for persistent

68 contrails, months in case of O_3 changes, and years for CH_4 and CH_4 -induced changes in
69 comparison to centuries for CO_2), allowing for quicker reductions in short-term warming, e.g.
70 by re-routing flights around PCFAs. However, such actions might increase CO_2 emissions
71 and operating costs, requiring ongoing efforts for balanced mitigation measures to reduce
72 aviation's climate impact. By contrast, mitigation of CO_2 offers climate benefits in the long
73 term. The challenge lies in finding the most effective trade-off between proven, effective CO_2
74 mitigation strategies and highly promising, yet uncertain, non- CO_2 options for addressing
75 climate change.

- 76 3. Calculating CO_2e is complex due to the diverse nature of non- CO_2 effects, requiring data
77 from weather, fuel composition, aircraft specifics, and flight monitoring. Therefore, it is
78 questionable whether the European non- CO_2 MRV system will be effective or merely increase
79 effort without delivering meaningful results.

80 Since uncertainties are inherent to all aspects of CO_2e calculation and will remain, policy imple-
81 mentation must address these by fostering risk assessment and impact evaluation while remaining
82 adaptable to new scientific developments and technological advancements. For an effective im-
83 plementation of such policies, a comprehensive evaluation of their effects is important, including
84 impact on climate, demand, ticket prices, airline operations, and overall network efficiency.

85 Therefore, our study investigates the impact of non- CO_2 pricing on flight routing, climate,
86 and ticket prices. For this, we perform sensitivity analyses to explore the implications of different
87 accounting options, considering varying weather conditions, climate metrics, and carbon prices.
88 While uncertainties in MRV systems primarily affect data accuracy and reporting, non- CO_2 pricing
89 introduces the risk of inadvertently incentivizing harmful re-routing, such as through inaccurate
90 predictions of PCFAs. Section 2 explores strategies for considering non- CO_2 uncertainties in policy
91 measures and provides a blueprint for integrating non- CO_2 pricing into operational flight planning.
92 Models and data used in this study are described in Section 3, including emission, climate response
93 and cost modeling as well as the simulation and optimization of flight trajectories. Section 4
94 presents the analysis results, highlighting dependencies on various policy design parameters and
95 meteorological characteristics. Lastly, we summarize the paper by discussing the results and by
96 providing concluding remarks in Section 5.

97 **2 Considering non- CO_2 effects in climate policies**

98 Our concept for integrating non- CO_2 pricing into climate policies is outlined in Section 2.1, pro-
99 viding a framework for calculating CO_2e and climate costs of single flights. Section 2.2 explores
100 strategies to address uncertainties associated with non- CO_2 effects and how to manage them in
101 pricing and flight planning.

Figure 1: Flowchart for integrating non-CO₂ aviation effects into flight planning procedures (pre-flight mode) and monitoring and reporting processes (post-flight mode) of AOs.

2.1 Schematic for integrating price-based CO₂e in operational flight planning

The integration of non-CO₂ effects into a policy instrument—such as the EU MRV framework—is often based on the principle of CO₂e emissions, a way of unitizing the impacts of all climate agents. Since the climate impact of CO₂ is well-understood and monitored, it is reasonable to compare the effect from non-CO₂ emissions in relation to one kilogram of CO₂. Hence, a CO₂e of any given climate agent is defined to cause the same climate effect as one kilogram of CO₂, based on a specific climate metric. The total CO₂e from all considered non-CO₂ effects thus defines the amount of emissions to be monitored and reported, and potentially the amount of emission allowances to be surrendered in the future.

Such a non-CO₂ MRV system is currently being set up by the EU and has to be made practicable for AOs. For flight planning (pre-flight mode) as well as for MRV (post-flight mode), all stakeholders need to be able to calculate CO₂e in an easy, transparent and predictable way (c.f. Figure 1). To reduce the operational effort to a minimum, a post-flight CO₂e estimation will be automatically performed by the non-CO₂ aviation effects tracking system (NEATS). All necessary data will be directly retrieved from third parties (secondary data) but can optionally be updated by the AO with actual flight monitoring (primary) data (c.f. Box 1 for details on both data sets).

Climate impact mitigation can be performed voluntarily or be incentivized by a CO₂e pricing mechanism in the future, which internalizes external costs through taxes, cap-and-trade systems, or

121 subsidies. When operators implement long-term mitigation options from both technical (e.g. new
122 fuels, innovative propulsion technologies, new aircraft designs) or operational side (e.g. intermediate
123 stop operations, flight altitude adjustments), CO₂e calculation, such as via NEATS, can be applied
124 in post-flight mode, as long as AOs upload relevant data. For mitigation purposes that concern
125 weather-based route adjustments for climate optimization (especially for contrail avoidance), or
126 targeted SAF use on specific flights, in contrast, the CO₂e calculation has to be integrated into the
127 flight planning processes (pre-flight mode, c.f. Figure 1). For CO₂e-optimized flight planning, fuel
128 and cost estimation must be linked to both an emissions module (c.f. Sec.3.1), in particular for
129 NO_x emissions, and a climate response module (c.f. Sec.3.2) to determine CO₂e for relevant agents,
130 all under consideration of uncertainties. This is particularly important in the case of CO₂e pricing,
131 where a direct tax on CO₂e emissions or a cap with tradable CO₂e allowances may be applied. To
132 account climate costs during flight planning, calculated CO₂e values have to be scaled with the
133 carbon price. Incorporating climate costs into the direct operating costs (DOC) of a flight provides
134 operators with a financial incentive to reduce their environmental impact.

135 Weather-dependent CO₂e costs can only be determined shortly before departure, whereas ticket
136 pricing is highly dynamic, with fares set well in advance based on demand fluctuations. To manage
137 this, airlines must incorporate estimated CO₂e costs into ticket prices at time of booking, possibly
138 based on historical CO₂e data. Airlines could safeguard against fluctuations in CO₂e prices by pre-
139 booking emission allowances for the estimated values, similar to fuel hedging. Even if additional
140 CO₂e costs are fully passed to passengers, airlines still aim to offer competitive fares, especially
141 in price-sensitive markets. If re-routing reduces additional costs, they can gain a competitive
142 advantage by offering lower prices or increase profit margins by retaining the difference between
143 actual and expected CO₂e costs.

144 While airlines can reduce CO₂e pricing through re-routing and hedging strategies to remain
145 competitive, these mechanisms have broader implications for aviation. They influence market
146 behavior by driving innovation and supporting sustainable practices, which can efficiently contribute
147 to achieving policy goals. However, effective implementation requires careful consideration of the
148 uncertainties to ensure that pricing accurately reflects the environmental impact without causing
149 negative unintended side effects (c.f. Sec. 2.2).

150 **2.2 Options for addressing uncertainties in policy measures**

151 When implementing non-CO₂ policies, it is essential to carefully consider different aspects of risks
152 associated with the high uncertainty of quantifying non-CO₂ effects: the risk of inadvertently
153 increasing the climate impact instead of reducing it, and the challenge of integrating effective risk
154 management into the policy. Proper policy design and monitoring are crucial to mitigate these
155 risks. Otherwise, policymakers may face unintended consequences that undermine climate goals,
156 industries could experience inefficiencies or higher costs, and society would have to bear the impact
157 if policies fail to effectively reduce the overall climate impact. To address uncertainties related to
158 CO₂e calculation, we propose options for the following three types of uncertainties:

159 **1. Weather-related uncertainties** can be addressed by using various ensembles of meteoro-

logical data sets (e.g. available from European Centre of Medium Range Weather Forecast, ECMWF) or by incorporating data from different weather services. One possible approach is to focus on areas where all ensemble members predict weather conditions prone to contrail formation, reducing the risk of unnecessary detours. An alternative approach would consider all areas where at least one ensemble member indicates a PCFA, reducing the risk of contrail formation. Figure 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of PCFAs for June 16th, 2018 based on ECMWF ERA5 ensemble data, highlighting regions where contrails consistently form over all ensembles (mean value of one; standard deviation of zero), as well as areas with larger variability. Higher standard deviations at the boundaries of predicted PCFAs indicate discrepancies in temperature and humidity predictions. By considering ensemble PCFAs, the risk of misidentifying contrail formation areas can be reduced, enhancing the reliability of mitigation strategies.

2. **Uncertainties in climate impact modeling of non-CO₂ effects** result from the complex nature of the atmosphere and the interactions between emissions and atmospheric processes. Scientists are continuously working to reduce these uncertainties by improving data collection, enhancing the understanding of physical and chemical processes, and refining models. To incorporate uncertainties in climate impact modeling into policy measures, the confidence intervals of each climate agent can be included in the CO₂e calculation. In this approach emitters must hold allowances for all non-CO₂ effects with a confidence level of e.g. greater than 80%, including only the 20% percentile of the climate impact of each agent in the CO₂e accounting (c.f. Sec. 3.3 & 4.2).
3. **Uncertainties in trajectory and emissions modeling** are generally smaller than those in weather and climate models. Fuel consumption is estimated during flight planning and closely monitored and recorded by the aircraft during flights to ensure fuel efficiency, safety, and operational effectiveness. Trajectory modeling, based on EUROCONTROLS BADA 3 and improved with BADA 4, has a mean error in fuel consumption lower than 5% (Nuic et al.,

Figure 2: Mean (top) and standard deviation (bottom) for areas of persistent contrail formation (PCFA) calculated with Clim-aCCF library for June 16th, 2018, based on ERA5 re-analysis ensemble members.

186 2010). Emission calculations, especially for NO_x , vary in accuracy depending on methods like
187 Boeing, DLR, or p_3T_3 , with uncertainties up to $\pm 10\%$ (c.f. Sec. 3.1; Schäfer and Bartosch,
188 2013). While continued research is needed to improve accuracy, these uncertainties are less
189 significant than those in weather and climate response and are not addressed in the following.

190 3 Models and Data

191 To investigate the influence of CO_2e accounting on flight planning (*policy-driven flight planning*),
192 we perform emissions and climate impact modeling (Section 3.1 and 3.2) as well as cost assessment
193 (Section 3.3) in the context of trajectory optimization (Section 3.4).

194 3.1 Emission modeling

195 Calculating the level of non- CO_2 emissions, particularly NO_x , soot¹ and water vapor, requires fuel
196 flow data estimations along the trajectory (c.f. Fig. 1). Emissions of CO_2 and H_2O are directly
197 proportional to fuel burn and can be estimated using fixed emission indices (EIs). In contrast,
198 NO_x emissions are a by-product caused by oxidation of nitrogen, contained in the air, under high
199 combustion temperatures and pressures, making them highly dependent on temperature and fuel-
200 air residence time. Hence, NO_x production correlates with flight conditions, fuel flow, and ambient
201 meteorological parameters like air pressure, temperature, humidity, and airspeed.

202 In this study, NO_x emissions are estimated using Boeing (2) Fuel Flow Method (BFFM2;
203 DuBois and Paynter, 2006), a standardized and ICAO-recommended approach (ICAO, 2020) that
204 enables automated calculations, e.g. as part of the NEATS tool. BFFM relies on certified sea-level
205 engine emission indices and fuel flow data from ICAOs Engine Exhaust Emissions Database (EDB)
206 (ICAO, 2023). The current parameter set is only valid for rich-burn, quick-mix, lean-burn (RQL)
207 combustors. A parameter set for lean-burn engines is currently being developed within ICAO but
208 has not yet been published.

209 3.2 Climate response modeling

210 Non- CO_2 effects in climate policies can be calculated using various climate response models. To
211 be suitable for policy applications, these models must compute different climate metrics for all
212 relevant climate agents on a per flight basis incorporating four-dimensional trajectories and current
213 weather conditions. This enables mitigation during operational route planning, particularly for
214 avoiding persistent contrails. Since not all available models cover all relevant climate agents and
215 not necessarily with equal precision, a combination of models may be necessary to ensure a robust
216 CO_2e modeling (c.f. Box 2).

217 In this study, we apply algorithmic climate change functions (aCCFs) to enable weather-
218 dependent CO_2e calculation of various climate agents for four-dimensional trajectories (Dietmüller
219 et al., 2023; Yin et al., 2021, 2023). aCCFs provide spatially and temporally resolved estimates of

¹We exclude direct and indirect soot effects from the following considerations due to the low level of scientific understanding and their limited mitigation potential in course of operational mitigation

220 average near-surface temperature change per emitted mass, allowing fast-time calculation of the
 221 individual climate effects during trajectory planning and optimization (c.f. Sec. 3.4) without com-
 222 plex chemistry-climate modeling. The application of aCCFs is regionally limited and their accuracy
 223 varies strongly with the atmospheric life-time of considered species. aCCFs cover the climate im-
 224 pact of CO₂, NO_x-induced O₃ and CH₄ changes, direct water vapor effects as well as persistent
 225 contrail formation, with different functions for night-time contrails (warming effect) and day-time
 226 contrails (warming and cooling effect).

227 Four-dimensional CO₂e functions in dependence of emission location and time are obtained as
 228 the temporal integral of aCCF_{*i*} multiplied with the fuel flow for CO₂, H₂O, emission flow for NO_x
 229 or the true airspeed v_{TAS} in the case of CiC:

$$CO_2e(x, t) = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \left(\sum_i \frac{aCCF_i(x, t) \cdot \dot{m}_{fuel}(t)}{aCCF_{CO_2}} + \frac{aCCF_{NO_x}(x, t) \cdot \dot{m}_{NO_x}(t)}{aCCF_{CO_2}} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{aCCF_{CiC}(x, t) \cdot v_{TAS}(t)}{aCCF_{CO_2}} \right) dt \cdot EI_{CO_2} \quad (1)$$

230 By using average values for emissions and flight distance per fuel burned, depending on aircraft
 231 category and altitude, the aCCFs per species can be summarized in one merged aCCF (aCCF_{merged})
 232 representing the climate impact from the considered non-CO₂ emission species H₂O, NO_x, and CiC:

$$CO_2e(x, t) = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \frac{aCCF_{merged}(x, t) \cdot \dot{m}_{fuel}(t)}{aCCF_{CO_2}} dt \cdot EI_{CO_2} \quad (2)$$

233 Here we introduce the concept of algorithmic cost functions for climate change (aCCCs), that
 234 are derived by multiplying CO₂e functions with carbon costs, specifically the price of European
 235 Union Aviation Allowances (EUAA):

$$aCCC(x, t) = CO_2e(x, t) \cdot EUAA \quad (3)$$

236 These functions represent climate cost in dependence of emission location and time to be applied
 237 in policy-driven trajectory optimization. aCCCs can be calculated for various climate metrics (c.f.
 238 Box 3), with conversion factors and efficacy parameters provided by Dietmüller et al. (2023) and
 239 Thor et al. (2023), which are summarized in Table 4.

240 **3.3 Modeling of operating costs, CO₂e charges, and ticket prices**

241 During trajectory simulation and optimization, the cost assessment is based on a simplified imple-
 242 mentation of the DOC method by TU Berlin, as applied in the Central Reference Aircraft data
 243 system (CeRAS) (Risse et al., 2016; Thorbeck and Scholz, 2013; Zengerling et al., 2023). DOCs
 244 are calculated as a function of mission distance d_j , fuel burn $m_{fuel,j}$ and flight time t_j , considering
 245 the cost of ownership, fuel, crew, maintenance, as well as navigation, landing and ground handling
 246 charges. Unit costs in dependence of aircraft category are derived from 2018 average airline cost
 247 data from the EU Horizon 2020 project ClimOP (Zengerling et al., 2023).

248 By implementing a policy that prices non-CO₂ effects, total operating cost (TOC) accounts for

249 both direct costs borne by AOs and indirect costs of climate change imposed on society. Inter-
 250 nalizing these costs helps policymakers promote more sustainable practices and mitigate negative
 251 externalities, in our case through non-CO₂ pricing. To model the TOC of a flight mission j , DOCs
 252 are extended with a climate change cost term, calculated by multiplying resulting CO₂e _{j} (c.f. Eq. 1
 253 and 2) with the EUAA price:

$$\text{TOC}_j = f_{\text{DOC}}(m_{\text{fuel},j}, t_j, d_j) + \text{CO}_2e_j \cdot \text{EUAA} \quad (4)$$

254 To relate cost changes to ticket prices, we use the average ticket price of 2023 for the analyzed
 255 routes j , provided by *Sabre Market Intelligence (MI) database* (Sabre, 2024), as reference ticket
 256 price $\text{TP}_{\text{Sabre2023},j}$. To evaluate the effects of surrendering CO₂e certificates on air fares, we assume
 257 that all additional costs (ΔTOC_j) are passed on to passengers ($n_{\text{PAX},j}$):

$$\text{TP}_j = \text{TP}_{\text{Sabre2023},j} + \Delta\text{TOC}_j \cdot n_{\text{PAX},j}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

258 We first calculate the impact of CO₂e pricing on ticket fares (ΔTP_j) in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 before
 259 we apply price elasticities (η) in Section 4.3 to estimate its impact on passenger demand:

$$\Delta n_{\text{PAX},j} = \eta \cdot \Delta\text{TP}_j \cdot \text{TP}_{\text{Sabre2023},j}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

260 3.4 Trajectory simulation and optimization

261 We apply DLR’s Python-based *Trajectory Optimization Module* (pyTOM) to develop eco-efficient
 262 trajectories (Lührs et al., 2016; Lau et al., 2022). In the latest version, pyTOM is combining the
 263 Theta* path planning algorithm with optimal control techniques. After computing a good initial
 264 solution with Theta*, an optimal control algorithm is applied to generate a feasible and dynamically
 265 optimal trajectory, taking into account a detailed flight performance model. Aircrafts motion is
 266 described as the temporal evolution of state variables (e.g., position, mass, emissions), which are
 267 modified using control variables (e.g., aircraft heading, thrust). Thrust, fuel flow and aerodynamic
 268 drag are obtained from EUROCONTROL’s Base of Aircraft Data Revision 4.2 (BADA) aircraft
 269 performance model in its python implementation (Nuic and Mouillet, 2012). Emission flows along
 270 the flight trajectory are calculated by the emission module (c.f. Sec. 3.1) by multiplying the fuel flow
 271 by the provided emission indices EI_i for CO₂, H₂O, and NO _{x} based on BFFM2. Optimized aircraft
 272 trajectories are determined by identifying a control input which minimizes a multi-objective cost
 273 functional \mathcal{J}_{MO} while satisfying dynamic constraints as well as control, state and path limitations.
 274 When determining climate-optimized trajectories, \mathcal{J}_{MO} is typically defined as the weighted sum of
 275 DOC (squared brackets) and climate impact (curly brackets), which is obtained as the temporal
 276 integral of aCCFs (c.f. Sec. 3.2) multiplied with the associated emission flow m_i . In case of CiC,
 277 climate impact is defined as a change in temperature per generated distance of cirrus. Here, the
 278 use of the CLIMaCCF open-source python library enables the normalization of CiC to the unit
 279 $[K \cdot kg_{\text{fuel}}^{-1}]$ based on averaged fuel efficiency values (Dietmüller et al., 2023). Similarly, NO _{x} emission
 280 indices are precomputed and averaged for a typical transatlantic fleet for multiple flight altitudes

Figure 3: Climate costs in € per kg fuel over Europe at 250 hPa on 16 June 2018 at 00:00 UTC (top) and 12:00 UTC (bottom), calculated using algorithmic cost functions for climate change (aCCC), assuming a carbon price of 80€.

281 to allow a unified calculation based on the fuel flow \dot{m}_i .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{J}_{\text{MO}} = & \omega_{\text{cost}} \cdot [f_{\text{DOC}}(m_{\text{fuel}}, t_j, d_j)] \cdot \text{DOC}_{\text{ref}}^{-1} \\
 & + \omega_{\text{clim}} \cdot \left\{ \sum_i \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \text{aCCF}_i(x, t) \cdot \dot{m}_i(t) dt \right\} \cdot \text{ATR}_{\text{ref}}^{-1} \\
 & i \in \{CO_2; H_2O; NO_x; \text{CiC}\},
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

282 where the monetary costs (DOC) and the climate impact (average temperature response, ATR)
 283 are normalized with respect to the corresponding reference values of the cost-optimized (minimum
 284 DOC) trajectory. For \mathcal{J}_{MO} , the Pareto optimal set is found by varying the weights $(\omega_{\text{cost}}, \omega_{\text{clim}}) \in$
 285 $[0; 1]$ with $\omega_{\text{cost}} + \omega_{\text{clim}} = 1$.

286 While climate-optimized routing typically balances climate impact (ATR) and operating cost
 287 (EUR), non- CO_2 pricing reduces the multi-objective cost functional \mathcal{J}_{MO} to a one-dimensional
 288 economic cost functional $\mathcal{J}_{\text{cost}}$:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{cost}} = \min \{ f_{\text{DOC}}(m_{\text{fuel}}, t_j, d_j) + CO_2 e_j \cdot \text{EUAA} \} \tag{8}$$

289 The continuous optimal control problem is transformed into a nonlinear programming problem
 290 (NLP) and solved using standard NLP solvers within pyTOM applying Dymos, an open-source
 291 Python library that extends OpenMDAO to solve optimal control and trajectory optimization
 292 problems in dynamic systems.

293 4 Simulation of policy-driven flight planning

294 The costs and benefits of policy-driven flight planning are investigated in the following with tra-
 295 jectory simulations for different weather patterns on two intra-European routes. To identify repre-
 296 sentative and interesting routes with regard to the climate impact, we base our investigations on a

Table 1: Study set-up with reference values in bold

	Considered variations
Missions	BCN-FRA and DUS-PMI
Temporal scope	16 th of every month of 2018 (June)
Accounting share	20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, 100%
CO ₂ e price	50€, 80€ , 110€
Metric	p-ATR ₁₀₀ , p-ATR ₅₀ , p-EGWP ₁₀₀ , p-EGWP ₅₀
Uncertainties	10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50% (median)
Contrail effects	Warming and cooling vs. warming only

297 flight schedule from the year 2023 as provided by Sabre (2024) MI data base. The focus is set on
 298 intra-European flight missions as the current non-CO₂ MRV is limited to these routes. Furthermore,
 299 we restrict the flight plan to the most relevant aircraft types in terms of passenger volume, namely
 300 to Airbus A320/A320neo family and Boeing 737/737MAX family. We limit the minimum flight
 301 distance to 750 km and pre-select routes based on the covered traffic volume in terms of avail-
 302 able seat kilometers (ASK). Finally, we identify two routes—one from Barcelona (BCN), Spain, to
 303 Frankfurt (FRA), Germany, and another from Düsseldorf (DUS), Germany, to Palma de Mallorca
 304 (PMI)—where contrail cirrus forms at one time of day and not at another, on the same selected case
 305 study day, 16th June 2018, making them particularly interesting for sensitivity studies (c.f. Fig. 3).
 306 Figure 3 illustrates the aCCCs over the European airspace on June 16, 2018 at 00:00 and 12:00
 307 UTC at 250hPa describing trajectory-dependent climate costs based on meteorological parameters.
 308 The color coding represents climate charges in € per kilogram of burnt fuel. Higher charges are
 309 indicated red and negative charges in dark blue. To capture seasonal variations, simulations were
 310 extended to include one day per month, using ECMWF’s ERA-5 weather data from the 16th day of
 311 each month in 2018. However, for real-time application during flight planning, forecast data will be
 312 essential. All trajectories are simulated with a current generation narrow-body BADA performance
 313 model in its python implementation (Nuic and Mouillet, 2012), assuming a constant cruise Mach
 314 number of 0.78 and a load factor of 90%. Since flight planning is currently typically optimized in
 315 terms of costs minimization, results from the following analysis, e.g. operating costs, ticket prices
 316 and CO₂e of each simulated trajectory, are expressed relative to corresponding values from the
 317 route-specific trajectory optimized for DOC (*‘Business as Usual’, BAU*).

318 Section 4.1 describes the conceptual approach of CO₂e-based accounting and its influence on
 319 policy driven flight planning. To consider different design parameters of possible policy approaches
 320 in case of CO₂e obligations, sensitivity analyses are conducted in Section 4.2 to investigate the in-
 321 fluence of (i) the CO₂e accounting option (full, step-wise, uncertainty-based), (ii) the carbon price
 322 (50, 80, 115 €/per ton of CO₂), and (iii) the climate metric (ATR and efficacy-weighted global warm-
 323 ing potential, EGWP, over 50 and 100 years based on pulse emissions, e.g., p-EGWP₁₀₀). Table
 324 1 summarizes the study set-up and the considered variations in course of the different sensitivity
 325 studies.

326 4.1 Incentive effect of non-CO₂ pricing

327 Figure 4 (top) shows the cost-optimized reference trajectory (BAU, without CO₂e accounting) for
 328 the flight from BCN to FRA on 16 June 2018 at 12:00UTC characterized by a high contrail climate
 329 effect. If CO₂e accounting is implemented, the flight trajectory of the reference mission is changed
 330 drastically especially in the vertical dimension to avoid regions of high climate cost, i.e. high climate
 331 sensitivity due to contrail-forming regions, indicated by colored contour lines in Figure 4. Thereby,
 332 CO₂e can be reduced by 55% compared to the reference case, demonstrating the suitability of CO₂e
 333 accounting to effectively reduce the climate impact along the trajectory.

334 The resulting cost-benefit potential in terms of CO₂e reduction and operating costs is shown
 335 in Figure 5. Without introducing a policy of CO₂e accounting, climate-optimized routings (black
 336 dots) need to balance the trade-off between two conflicting objectives: minimizing costs (fuel,
 337 time, or operating expenses) on the one hand and reducing climate impact (given in CO₂e in this
 338 example) on the other hand. Typically, higher climate mitigation potentials are associated with
 339 higher operating costs, creating a *'win-lose' situation*. By contrast, an implementation of CO₂e
 340 accounting extends the TOC by the broader societal costs associated with the resulting climate
 341 effect. Hence, absolute cost for AOs increase, as indicated by the red dot in Fig. 5. However, a
 342 large share of these additional costs can be reduced by adopting more sustainable practices, like
 343 climate-optimized routings in this example. Since the policy specifies both the CO₂e calculation
 344 methodology and a carbon price (in this example full CO₂e accounting measured in p-ATR₁₀₀ at
 345 80 € per ton of CO₂, c.f. Table 1), there is only one cost-optimized solution, represented by the
 346 blue dot in Fig. 5 rather than multiple equivalent Pareto-optimal solutions (black dots).

347 In this example of a CiC-intensive mission, the mitigation potential of 55% can either be achieved
 348 voluntarily by accepting a 1.3% increase in operating cost or by incentivisation through CO₂e
 349 accounting (blue dot). The CO₂e accounting scenario results in 12.5% higher costs compared
 350 to today's BAU trajectory costs (black star, no accounting, no re-routing) but is 18.6% cheaper
 351 than the BAU costs when CO₂e accounting is applied (red dot). Compared to today's costs,
 352 the expansion of the balance by CO₂e leads to cost increase across all trajectories. However, if
 353 the extended balancing is embraced as the new reference (green line), the re-routed trajectory
 354 becomes the most cost-efficient, creating a win-win scenario with a financial incentive of a 17.2%
 355 cost reduction while minimizing climate impact. By narrowing the choices to a single, most cost-

Figure 4: Cost-optimized trajectories in vertical plot considering DOC optimization without CO₂e accounting (top) and with CO₂e accounting (bottom) assuming a full accounting, exemplary for a reference mission from BCN to FRA on June 16, 2018 at 12:00 UTC.

Figure 5: Cost-benefit potential displayed in relative operating cost in relation relative reduction in CO₂e, exemplary for a full accounting along a mission from BCN to FRA on June 16, 2018 at 12:00 UTC

356 efficient route, the policy enables a simple and more socially responsible decision-making.

357 4.2 Sensitivities towards policy design parameters

358 Assuming that aircraft operators pass on all cost increases directly to their passenger, additional
 359 costs from climate effect internalization may increase ticket prices, potentially impacting affordabil-
 360 ity and consumer behavior. On this basis, Figures 6 (a) - (h) illustrate the impact on ticket prices
 361 (per passenger) for the examined routes with varying contrail intensity (horizontal dimension) and
 362 in dependence of differences in design parameters determining the CO₂e-based accounting (vertical
 363 dimension). While the policy framework in general works independently of the chosen CO₂e allo-
 364 cation method, carbon price, and climate metric, these design parameters can significantly impact
 365 the available mitigation options and associated ticket price changes. Such parameters include the
 366 definition of the (i) accounting scope (i.e. a gradual accounting of non-CO₂ effects considering
 367 only a share of their impact in the pricing scheme), (ii) the consideration of uncertainties related
 368 to the quantification of non-CO₂ climate effects, (iii) the level of the CO₂e price per kg, and (iv)
 369 the climate metric used to determine CO₂e. Sensitivities from different CO₂e allocation methods,
 370 carbon prices and climate metrics are investigated in the following according to the constraints
 371 displayed in table 1.

372 Weather situation

373 The weather situation along the investigated missions significantly influences the climate mitigation
 374 potential that can be obtained from policy-driven flight planning. Contrail-forming regions, with
 375 their high climate sensitivity and limited extent, offer significant mitigation potential for re-routing.
 376 For missions not crossing these regions, additional mitigation can be achieved by minimizing climate

Figure 6: Changes in ticket price and climate impact (CO_2e) in dependence of policy design parameters, namely accounting share (a-b), consideration of uncertainties (c-d), CO_2e prices (e-f), and climate metric (g-h). Results are displayed for exemplary missions from BCN to FRA on June 16th, 2018, low contrail intensity (left) and with high contrail intensity (right) along the mission

377 sensitivity from NO_x and H_2O effects. However, as these effects cannot be fully avoided and
 378 have markedly smaller climate impact gradients, overall mitigation is lower than for CiC-intensive
 379 missions (c.f. Figure 6). The mitigation potential of the CiC-intensive mission (up to 55% compared
 380 to the reference case, filled marker in Fig. 6, right) is notably higher compared to the mission
 381 without contrails (up to 10% compared to the reference case, filled marker in Fig. 6, left). This is
 382 consistent with findings from analyses on climate-optimized trajectories indicating higher climate
 383 mitigation potentials for CiC-intensive missions [e.g. Grewe et al. (2017); Lührs et al. (2016, 2021);
 384 Teoh et al. (2022); Martin Frias et al. (2024)]. However, the resulting cost increase and additional

385 ticket prices do not differ significantly between both examples. The ticket price increase for the
 386 most cost-efficient solution ranges from 7.50€ (no contrails) to 8.40€ (with contrails). Without
 387 re-routing, the ticket price would increase by 8.1€ or 24.0€.

388 Accounting method

389 Integrating non-CO₂ effects into existing CO₂ accounting schemes influences both climate mitiga-
 390 tion potential and ticket prices, requiring careful selection of allocation methods. As with EU ETS
 391 (no surrender obligation in 2010 and 2011, CAP decrease over time) and CORSIA (baseline period,
 392 voluntary and mandatory phases), a step-wise introduction allows operators to adapt and imple-
 393 ment more sustainable practices. We therefore model different accounting options that moderate
 394 ticket price increases while ensuring effective policy implementation:

- 395 1. Full CO₂e accounting: Emitters must hold permits for all calculated CO₂e.
- 396 2. Step-wise CO₂e accounting: Emitters must hold permits for, e.g., 20% of calculated CO₂e in
 397 the first year ($n + 1$), with the share gradually increasing over time (e.g., 40% in year $n + x$,
 398 60% in year $n + y$).
- 399 3. Uncertainty-based CO₂e accounting: Emitters must hold permits for all calculated CO₂e
 400 values of a climate agent with a confidence level of e.g. greater than 80% (c.f. Sec. 2.2).

401 Uncertainty-based accounting aligns allocation with the current scientific understanding in climate-
 402 response modeling. To implement this, we estimated the probability density functions for CiC, H₂O
 403 and NO_x (c.f. Fig. 7), based on best estimates and 5-95% confidence intervals from Lee et al. (2021),
 404 assuming a Pearson distribution for NO_x and a Gaussian distribution for the others. Based on these
 405 distributions, we obtain, for example, a 20th percentile ERF of 37.0 mW/m² for CiC (64% of the
 406 median) and 8.8 mW/m² for NO_x (56% of the median, c.f. Tab. 5).

Figure 7: Estimated probability density functions for (a) cirrus contrails assuming a Gaussian normal distribution and (b) NO_x assuming a Pearson distribution (derived from Lee et al., 2021)

407 Implication of both approaches are shown in Figure 6, a - d. In the CiC-intensive case, a 20%
408 gradual CO₂e accounting reduces the climate by 27.4% with a 2.20€ ticket price increase, while
409 increasing the accounting to 60% enhances mitigation to 47.6% at a cost of 5.30€. In the case
410 without CiC, mitigation potentials are lower but ticket price changes are similar.

411 Uncertainty-based accounting (c.f. Figure 7 and Sec. 2.2) shows a strong correlation between
412 uncertainty levels and mitigation potential. At high confidence levels (low percentiles), the ac-
413 counted CO₂e share is significantly higher than with gradual accounting. For example, at 90%
414 confidence (10th percentile), 45% of the median CO₂e is accounted for CiC and H₂O, and 26% for
415 NO_x, resulting in 46.8% mitigation and a 3.00€ ticket price increase in the CiC-intensive example
416 (c.f. Fig. 6, d). The mitigation potential of the 20th percentile corresponds roughly to 60% gradual
417 accounting, while the 30th percentile aligns with 80%. Accordingly, the uncertainty based approach
418 is more progressive than a gradual accounting, leading to higher mitigation potentials and ticket
419 prices.

420 CO₂e pricing

421 The results from the accounting scheme for non-CO₂ effects depends on the EUAA price level,
422 i.e., the cost of CO₂e allowances. Historic emission allowance prices have fluctuated between 7€
423 (2012) and 84€ (2023) since aviation joined the EU ETS (European Energy Exchange, 2024).
424 Future prices remain uncertain due to supply-demand dynamics, but with increasing LRF, expiring
425 free allocations, and potential inclusion of non-CO₂ effects, further increases are likely. van den
426 Bergh and Botzen (2015) reviewed social carbon costs (SCC) and deemed values below 125 USD
427 unrealistic.

428 To assess EUAA price impacts on re-routing, prices are varied between 50€, 80€ (2023 refer-
429 ence), and 115 € per ton of CO₂ (approx. 125 USD at a 2015 exchange rate).

430 As shown in Fig. 6 (ef), higher CO₂e prices result in greater ticket price increases for passengers:
431 For example, with a lower price level of 50€, we observe ticket price increases of 5.70€ for the CiC-
432 intensive mission (4.90€ for the no-CiC mission) while a higher price level of 115€ leads to ticket
433 price increases of 11.90€ (10.50€). However, climate mitigation potentials are affected to a smaller
434 extent as they vary between 54.5% and 56.1% (6.5% and 13.4%). In general, the climate mitigation
435 potentials are less sensitive to the CO₂e prices in comparison to the accounting shares (both gradual
436 and uncertainty based). In contrast, the prices of allowances significantly determine the ticket price
437 increase and thus economic effects on airlines and passengers.

438 Climate metric

439 For assessing the CO₂e level of a single flight (pulse emission), we focus on p-ATR and p-EGWP
440 over 50 and 100 years. With long atmospheric lifetimes of CO₂, the balance between CO₂ and
441 non-CO₂ effects is shifted more towards CO₂ for longer time horizons, while non-CO₂ effects are
442 predominant when investigating shorter time horizons. Therefore, we observe higher mitigation
443 potentials for climate metrics of shorter time-horizon. For example, the CiC-intensive mission
444 achieves a 61% CO₂e reduction with p-ATR₅₀, compared to 55% for p-ATR₁₀₀ (c.f. Figure 6, h).
445 This trend holds for p-EGWP, e.g. 58% for p-EGWP₅₀ and 52% for p-EGWP₁₀₀, though with

446 lower mitigation potential than p-ATR due to a lower relative weight of non-CO₂ effects compared
 447 to CO₂ effects. Differences in ticket price changes are influenced by the share of non-CO₂ effects
 448 in total CO₂e. Metrics that result in a higher share of non-CO₂ effects lead to higher ticket price
 449 increases compared to those with a lower share of non-CO₂ effects. For example, considering p-
 450 ATR₅₀ results in a ticket price increase of approximately 15€ in the CiC-intensive case (13.20€ for
 451 the mission without contrails), while p-EGWP₁₀₀ results in an increase of 6.80€ (6.00€).

452 **4.3 Cost implications of CO₂e pricing under varying weather scenarios**

453 After demonstrating the high weather dependency of non-CO₂e pricing in Section 4.2, we repeat
 454 the analysis for different weather situations, specifically for one day of each month in 2018.

455 **Impact of different weather situations on ticket fares**

456 In Figure 8a, each dashed black line represents the impact of a gradual accounting on CO₂e mit-
 457 igation and ticket prices for a particular weather situation. The strong variations between these
 458 Pareto lines, particularly in the horizontal dimension, show that weather conditions, especially
 459 the presence or absence of PCFAs, are the primary drivers of mitigation potential. Ticket price
 460 changes remain within the same order of magnitude across different weather scenarios, while higher
 461 sensitivities are observed regarding the accounting share (c.f. color variations in Fig. 8a). This is
 462 because CO₂e optimized flights largely avoid PCFAs, especially when accounting shares are high.
 463 As a result, most of the remaining additional CO₂e costs come from NO_x and H₂O emissions,
 464 which are significantly less influenced by weather conditions than CiC. Design parameters of the
 465 pricing mechanism—such as carbon price, climate metric, or accounting method—can thus influence
 466 the incentive effect or reduce the additional burden on airlines, but their impact is less significant
 467 compared to the variation in weather conditions.

Table 2: Additional CO₂e charge per ticket relative to the 25th percentile, mean, and 7th percentile ticket prices in 2023.

Ticket fare		Additional CO ₂ e charge per ticket				
		2€	4€	6€	8€	10€
25 th	118.80€	1.7%	3.4%	5.0%	6.7%	8.4%
mean	206.71€	1.0%	1.9%	2.9%	3.9%	4.8%
75 th	288.43€	0.7%	1.4%	2.1%	2.8%	3.5%

468 To assess the impact of CO₂e pricing on ticket fares, we relate this to the overall ticket fares
 469 and their variation over time. Airlines use dynamic pricing models where ticket prices fluctuate
 470 based on booking time, capacity utilization, and demand. While fares must cover operating costs
 471 (e.g., fuel, staff, maintenance, airport charges) in the long term, short-term prices are primarily
 472 demand-driven—rising with high demand and dropping through discounts when demand is low. In
 473 2023, ticket prices for Western European flights showed considerable variation (c.f. Fig. 8b) with
 474 BCN-FRA average fares from 169€ (November) to 275€ (February) and strong seasonal effects. The
 475 additional CO₂e charge per ticket results in an average fare increase of 1.0%-4.8%. For example,

Figure 8: (a) Variation of ticket price increases and associated CO₂e mitigation potentials in dependence of different weather situations (16th day of each month in 2018) for a mission from BCN to FRA. (b) Sabre ticket fare statistics of the year 2023 for selected Western European flights.

476 at the 25th percentile, an additional CO₂e charge of 2€ would increase the ticket price by 1.7%,
 477 while at the 75th percentile, the same charge would represent a 0.7% increase. Higher charges,
 478 such as 10€ per ticket, would lead to increases of up to 8.4% at the 25th percentile and 3.5% at
 479 the 75th percentile (c.f. Table2). These increases, although noticeable, remain relatively small in
 480 comparison to the overall fare fluctuations, which can range by up to several hundred euros over
 481 the course of the year. Even though, non-CO₂e pricing will increase ticket fares on average, low and
 482 high fares are expected to be less affected as they are primary demand-driven by dynamic pricing.

483 Impact of CO₂e pricing on passenger demand

484 Price elasticity in air travel measures how demand responds to ticket price changes, varying by route,
 485 distance, passenger type, and market conditions. Aggregated elasticities capture both price-driven
 486 demand changes on the same route and of substitutes, making them crucial for policy evaluation as
 487 market-wide price increases from taxes or CO₂e pricing also affect alternatives (Kölker et al., 2023).
 488 For Fit-for-55 impact analysis, studies use aggregated elasticity values of -0.63 (Oxera, 2022), -0.87
 489 (Oesingmann and Kölker, 2025) and -1.11 (Scheelhaase et al., 2021).

490 Assuming a price elasticity of -0.87, CO₂e pricing reduces demand by 0.8% to 4.2%, as shown
 491 in Table 3.

Table 3: Possible impact of additional CO₂e charge on passenger demand, assuming an aggregated price elasticity of -0.87.

Ticket fare	Additional CO ₂ e charge per ticket				
	2€	4€	6€	8€	10€
206.71€	0.8%	1.7%	2.5%	3.4%	4.2%

492 To get a rough estimate of the combined effect of CO₂e-driven price changes and forecasted
493 passenger growth on demand, we multiply the median demand reduction of 2.5% for average ticket
494 fares with the European passenger growth rate of the ICAO’s mean post-COVID-19 forecast sce-
495 nario of 3.7% (2021). The result is a decline in the projected European annual passenger growth
496 of -2.7% to 1.1%.

497 **Abatement costs of CO₂e avoidance**

498 The cost of CO₂e avoidance is primarily driven by operational expenses, caused by changes in fuel
499 burn and flight time, but might also be influenced by possible capital investments in infrastruc-
500 ture, including satellites, ground cameras, and humidity sensors on aircraft. Our study focuses
501 on operational expenses and finds abatement costs for a full mitigation, excluding CO₂e costs,
502 ranging from 2.8 to 74.4 € per tonne of CO₂e (median: 14.1€, mean 19.0€) on the exemplary mis-
503 sion BCNFRA under varying weather conditions. The lowest abatement costs occur when contrail
504 avoidance is effective, while the highest costs arise on days without PCFAs. Other studies focusing
505 exclusively on contrail mitigation estimate abatement costs to range between 1 and 25€/tCO₂e by
506 2040 (Cathcart et al., 2024; Martin Frias et al., 2024; Google, nd; T&E, 2023). Compared to other
507 sectors, operational CO₂e avoidance in aviation appears cost-effective, with estimated abatement
508 costs lower than those of wind (82 to 276€ in Germany and Spain; Abrell et al., 2019)² and solar
509 power (411 to 1,944€ in Germany and Spain; Abrell et al., 2019)² or direct air carbon capture and
510 storage (USD 341 to 374 per ton CO₂ at a cumulative capacity of 1 GtCO₂ per year; Sievert et al.,
511 2024).

512 **Pricing of cooling contrails**

513 Since contrails can also have a cooling effect during the day, this effect could be incorporated into a
514 pricing mechanism, where flights generating cooling CiC may be eligible for economic compensation
515 for operators. This effect can be observed on a simulated flight from Düsseldorf (DUS) to Palma de
516 Mallorca (PMI) on 16 July 2018. In the given example, the BAU reference trajectory (c.f. Fig. 9,
517 top right) passes through the center of a warming contrail area while staying below a cooling region.
518 This routing leverages tailwinds and avoids headwinds to save costs and flight time. Without re-
519 routing, this would result in significant additional costs under a CO₂e pricing scheme (Fig. 4, left,
520 red symbols). However, by adjusting the flight path to a neighboring area with cooling contrails
521 (c.f. Fig. 9, bottom right), these costs could be neutralized assuming a 20% CO₂e accounting
522 scheme or even lead to price savings at higher accounting levels. If 100% of these additional costs
523 were passed on to passengers, ticket prices would be reduced by 1.5€(60% CO₂e accounting, blue
524 upward-pointing triangle b), 2.6€(80%, blue diamond), or 3.6€(100%, blue circle). Due to the
525 strong cooling effect of alternative routing, the climate impact decreases significantly alongside
526 ticket prices by 82.8%, 89.7%, and 94.0%, respectively.

527 However, the active generation of cooling contrails is discussed much more controversially in the
528 scientific community than the avoidance of warming contrails. While avoiding warming contrails is

²It is important to note that these figures are based on data from 2017. Given the rapid advancements in renewable energy technologies and decreasing costs, current abatement costs are likely lower.

Figure 9: Changes in ticket price and CO₂e mitigation from cooling contrail effects for a mission from DUS to PMI on July 16, 2018 at 12:00 UTC (left), based on cost-based re-routing of flight trajectories (right): vertical plots of the BAU trajectory (top) and the 40% CO₂e accounting scenario (bottom)

generally seen as a promising climate mitigation measure, actively increasing artificial cloud cover through geo-engineering is considered riskier due to the uncertainties and complexity of atmospheric processes, with a higher potential for unintended consequences. Another critical issue is the moral hazard: the possibility of using artificial cooling to mitigate short-term temperature increases could be seen as a substitute for deep emission reductions, leading to neglect of necessary structural measures. Proponents of actively generating cooling contrails, on the other hand, emphasize the immediate cooling effects and argue that a policy focused solely on avoiding warming contrails could create an incentive asymmetry. Without actively promoting cooling contrails, an imbalance might arise that fails to fully exploit the potential for short-term mitigation of global temperature rise.

To prevent additional risks associated with incentivized geo-engineering, we have focused exclusively on persistent warming contrails in all other analyses, excluding cooling contrails from consideration. In the case of cooling PCFAs, CO₂e values account solely for other trace substances.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

Our study investigates the implications of non-CO₂ pricing on flight routing, climate impact and ticket prices across various weather conditions, CO₂e accounting options, climate metrics, and carbon prices. We find that the climate mitigation potential is primarily affected by route and weather characteristics while policy design parameters, like accounting shares or the choice of climate metric, play a secondary role. Since CO₂e-optimized flights largely avoid PCFAs, the remaining CO₂e costs are mainly due to NO_x and H₂O emissions, which are less sensitive to weather variations than CiC. In contrast, ticket price increases are strongly influenced by the accounted share of CO₂e values and the carbon price, suggesting that a gradual implementation—such as starting with 20% of the calculated (median) CO₂e values—could help to moderate the impact on

552 AOs and passengers. Due to significant ticket price fluctuations throughout the year, we observe
553 modest fare increases with CO₂e pricing. In our study, a 6€ ticket price increase—representing
554 a typical order of magnitude for 60% accounting—resulted in an average ticket prices increase of
555 2.9%, suggesting that the overall cost impact of CO₂e pricing is small compared to broader market
556 variations. Even though, non-CO₂e pricing will increase ticket fares on average, low and high fares
557 are expected to be less affected as they are demand-driven rather than cost-based. By applying an
558 aggregated price elasticity of -0.78 and a forecasted 3.7% European passenger growth rate, CO₂e
559 pricing reduces demand growth to 1.1%.

560 Since CO₂e charges are set just before departure, but fares are priced in advance, airlines
561 must incorporate estimated CO₂e costs into ticket prices at booking. Even if CO₂e costs are
562 passed to passengers, airlines seek competitive fares. If re-routing can lower costs, AOs can gain a
563 competitive advantage by offering lower prices or increase profit margins by keeping the difference
564 between actual and expected costs. Incorporating cooling contrails into a pricing mechanism could
565 neutralize or even reduce costs of affected flights through compensation but poses higher risks and
566 moral concern. In our study, abatement costs for CO₂e mitigation range from 3 to 74 € per tonne
567 with lower costs on days with effective contrail avoidance. These costs are relatively low compared
568 to mitigation measures from other sectors such as wind or solar energy and direct air capture.

569 CO₂e policies must be simple and clear to facilitate compliance, incentivize sustainable opera-
570 tions and technologies, and align with existing regulations, such as EU ETS and CORSIA, to avoid
571 conflicts. However, the saturation effect of contrails complicates their design: since the behavior of
572 other operators remains uncertain, accurately reflecting the non-linear relationship between traffic
573 density and warming in a transparent and predictable pricing mechanism is challenging. This is
574 particularly relevant in congested airspaces, where completely avoiding PCFAs is often infeasible,
575 and re-routing a few flights may lead to additional costs with minimal mitigation effects. Never-
576 theless, standardized climate effect estimates, disregarding saturation effects, can still be addressed
577 through compensation payments, such as the purchase of CO₂e allowances.

578 Rather than engaging on the complex process of CO₂e calculation and pricing, a proposed
579 alternative is to impose an aircraft-specific climate transit charge for highly climate-sensitive areas
580 (e.g., € per kilometer flown) such as PCFAs (Niklaß et al., 2021). This charge, similar to en-route
581 and terminal fees, could be based on aircraft weight and technology. Continuous, weather-based
582 updates on the position and level of these transit charges would allow operators and ANSPs to
583 seamlessly integrate climate costs into flight planning, facilitating simplified trajectory adjustments
584 without emissions monitoring or complex climate modeling.

585 To gain operational experience, mitigation efforts could start in regions with high climate im-
586 pact but lower operational complexity, such as the North Atlantic Track System (NATS)—a major
587 contributor to aviation emissions, organized through a simplified track system (OTS) due to lim-
588 ited radar coverage. Kandur (2020) integrated climate considerations into NAT-OTS design for
589 eight characteristic weather situations, showing that a daily optimization of tracks that minimize
590 headwind and the probability of crossing PCFAs can significantly reduce aviations climate impact
591 with only a slight increase in flight time.

592 Implementing CO₂e policies within a specific region, like the EU, must ensure global compet-

593 itiveness by avoiding disadvantages for local operators while fostering innovation and preserving
594 economic efficiency. Future research is therefore needed to explore how different geographical
595 scopes—such as a full coverage, including all flights regardless of origin or destination, or a reduced
596 scope, limited to intra-European flights—affect passenger demand and airline network dynamics,
597 including market competition between airlines. To accurately capture these effects, we plan to
598 expand our analysis using a discrete choice model, which provides a more detailed representation
599 of passenger preferences, substitution behaviors, and demand responses to changes in fares, travel
600 time, and service quality.

601 As non-CO₂ uncertainties are inherent and will persist, it is crucial to develop strategies to
602 manage them. While uncertainties in MRV systems mainly impact data accuracy and reporting,
603 non-CO₂ pricing risks inadvertently incentivizing harmful re-routing, for example, due to inaccurate
604 weather forecasts. If these risks remain unaddressed, policies could prioritize uncertain short-
605 term non-CO₂ reductions over proven long-term CO₂ mitigation, thus undermining overall climate
606 goals. To address this, we propose strategies to mitigate these risks. One approach uses ensemble
607 weather forecasts to either minimize unnecessary detours by focusing on consistent PCFAs or reduce
608 contrail formation risks by considering all potential PCFAs. Another approach is uncertainty-
609 based CO₂e accounting, where emitters must hold permits for CO₂e values of a climate agent
610 based on confidence levels in climate-impact modeling. Our results indicate that uncertainty-
611 based accounting is more progressive than a comparable gradual accounting, resulting in higher
612 mitigation potentials and increased ticket prices. Continued research, validation, and targeted risk
613 assessments are essential to improve the accuracy of non-CO₂ effects modeling and ensure the policy
614 effectively drives meaningful climate action in the aviation sector. Occasional higher impacts from
615 individual flights might be acceptable, if the majority of flights contribute to reducing the overall
616 annual climate impact with minimal risk. Non-CO₂ policies must be adaptable to new technologies,
617 fuels, and scientific findings, enabling the gradual reduction of these uncertainties. The multitude
618 of effects of CO₂e pricing, coupled with the risk of misguided mitigation incentives, necessitates
619 thorough investigation.

620 **Acknowledgements**

621 This work is part of the EU Horizon project Better Contrail Mitigation (BeCoM), funded by the European
622 Union (Grant agreement ID: 101056885). The authors thank Florian Wozny for a thorough internal review.

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Box 1: Primary and secondary data sets of the proposed European non-CO₂ MRV system

The proposed system consists of primary and secondary data. Primary data is private AO data, i.e. flight plan and monitored data. Secondary data is collected at a central repository (an enhanced EU-ETS support facility) with tailored access for the involved parties. It consists of flight trajectory data (by EUROCONTROL), meteorological data (from weather services) and conservative pre-filled data estimates for all aircraft, fuel and flight specifics. Possibly also quick access interfaces to the services are an option for the third-party data to reduce need for data storage. The term 'conservative' here means that using these estimates must not lead to lower CO₂e than with monitored flight data. The secondary data repository shall serve as a platform for easy reporting (see below), for filling data gaps and for allowing authorities to perform cross-checks of reported data. AOs can hence either create reports by themselves, using their own data, or let the authority conduct the reports for them based on pre-filled values. This largely reduces administrative MRV effort for the AO, however, as the pre-filled values are conservative, CO₂e will be greater than in the latter case. To reduce the need for conservative values when reporting is based on secondary data, AOs can optionally upload actual flight monitoring data to the secondary data repository. This will lower their CO₂e in the reports. For verification of the CO₂e reports, the AO has to provide the accredited verifier access to the primary data. Reporting data is the information submitted to the authority at the end of the reporting period (e.g. one year). It is the minimum data to assign CO₂ and CO₂e emissions of an AO per flight. All other information can remain with the operator. As in current EU-ETS for CO₂, the competent authority has to approve the AOs reports. For this, cross-checks using secondary data can be applied. Only in case of large deviations from reported and expected CO₂e values, authorities might ask AOs for primary data to validate the reports.

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Box 2: Overview of available climate response models

The climate response model AirClim (Grewe and Stenke, 2008; Dahlmann et al., 2016) evaluates basic aircraft/engine configurations and general operational strategies, estimating the impact of all non-CO₂ effects per flight on a climatological basis without weather dependence. CoCIP (Contrail Cirrus Prediction Tool; Schumann, 2012), a Lagrangian model, analyses contrail formation, life cycle and contrail climate effects based on flight and weather information but excludes other climate effects. LinClim (Lim et al., 2007), assesses global RF and temperature impacts, predicting responses of climatological aviation perturbation and monetary values of impacts. However, it currently prescribes RF only of aviation non-CO₂ effects. FaIR (Finite-amplitude Impulse-Response; Millar et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2018), a reduced-complexity climate model, and OSCAR (Gasser et al., 2017; Terrenoire et al., 2019), a compact Earth system model, compute global temperature responses based on emission scenarios but do not account for individual flights. LEEA (Low Emissions Effect Aircraft project; Köhler et al., 2008; Rädcl and Shine, 2008) calculates the climate impact of CO₂ and non-CO₂ effects, but lacks 3D trajectory considerations. aCCFs (algorithmic Climate Change Functions; Dietmüller et al., 2023) computes 4D effects of all non-CO₂ climate forces for individual flight planning cost-efficiently implemented directly in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models to consider current meteorological conditions.

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Box 3: The role of climate metrics in evaluating aviation’s climate impact

Different climate metrics assess aviation’s climate impact based on an indicator (e.g. effective radiative forcing, ERF), a time horizon (e.g., 20, 50, 100 or 500 years), and an emission scenario (e.g., pulse, sustained, or increasing emissions) (Fuglestedt et al., 2010). Common indicators like ERF, GWP and ATR differ in their sensitivity to these factors. Shorter time horizons (e.g., 20 years) emphasize near-term impacts, while longer ones (e.g., 100 years) align with sustainability goals (Grewe et al., 2015; Megill et al., 2024). Pulse emissions are recommended for single-flight assessments, whereas constant emissions suit long-term technology evaluations. Emission scenarios also affect the weighting of short- vs. long-lived climate agents, with pulse emissions over long horizons emphasizing CO₂, while shorter horizons highlight short-lived species (Grewe et al., 2015).

Selecting an appropriate climate metric is challenging due to the the considerable uncertainties associated with aviation’s non-CO₂ climate impacts, which differ based on atmospheric lifetimes, emission locations, and altitude. According to Megill et al. (2024), an ideal climate metric should remain neutral across different emission types, be stable over time, align with existing climate policies, and be straightforward to understand and implement. Their research recommends using ATR and EGWP with a time horizon of more than 70 years for climate policies.

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Table 4: The following conversion factors, provided by Dietmüller et al. (2023) and Thor et al. (2023), were used to convert p-ATR₂₀ to other metrics.

Conversion	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-ATR ₅₀	1.588	0.709	0.709
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-ATR ₁₀₀	1.801	0.446	0.446
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-EGWP ₅₀	216.970	66.220	66.220
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-EGWP ₁₀₀	343.028	66.220	66.220
Conversion	CH ₄	CiC	PMO
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-ATR ₅₀	1.061	0.709	1,061
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-ATR ₁₀₀	0.758	0.446	0.758
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-EGWP ₅₀	114.644	66.171	114.644
p-ATR ₂₀ → p-EGWP ₁₀₀	116.381	66.171	116.381

Table 5: Considered share of climate impact with uncertainty-based accounting

Percentiles	10th	20th	30th	40th	50th
CiC, H ₂ O	45.3%	64.5%	78.4%	90.6%	100.0%
NO _x	26.3%	56.0%	77.1%	94.3%	100.0%